

Oxidation of aliphatic primary alcohols by morpholinium chlorochromate : A kinetic and mechanistic approach

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Abstract : The oxidation of nine aliphatic primary alcohols by morpholinium chlorochromate (MCC) in dimethylsulfoxide leads to the transformation of alcohols to the corresponding aldehydes. The reaction is first order with respect to both MCC and the alcohol both. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of [1,1-²H₂]ethanol (MeCD₂OH) exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect. The reaction has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect was analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The rate of oxidation is susceptible to both polar and steric effects of the substituents. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : Correlation analysis, halochromates, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation.

Introduction

Oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds is an important transformation in synthetic organic chemistry. A large number of oxidants are known to bring about this transformation¹⁻⁵. Morpholinium chlorochromate (MCC) is also one of such compounds used for the oxidation of benzylic alcohols⁶. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by complexed Cr^{VI} species and a few reports have already reported from our laboratory^{7,8}. In continuation of our earlier work with Cr^{VI}, we report here the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of nine aliphatic primary alcohols by MCC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. The mechanistic aspects are discussed. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and discussion

The oxidation of alcohols results in the formation of corresponding aldehydes. The overall reaction may be represented as eq. (1).

MCC undergoes two-electron change. This is in accordance with the earlier observations with PFC⁹, PCC¹⁰ and MCC⁸ also.

Rate laws : The reaction is first order with respect to MCC. Further the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , is independent of the initial concentration of MCC. The reaction is first order with respect to the alcohol also (Table 1).

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile : The oxidation of alcohols, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile did not affect the rate. This indicates that a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely in the present reaction (Table 1).

Effect of temperature : The rates of oxidation of ten primary alcohols were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions (Table 1). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form given by the equation : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The values of a and b , for ethanol, are $9.38 \pm 0.19 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $14.9 \pm 0.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9981$).

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of ethanol by MCC at 298 K

10^3 [MCC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Alcohol] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.10	0.00	8.95
1.00	0.20	0.00	19.5
1.00	0.40	0.00	39.6
1.00	0.60	0.00	61.2
1.00	0.80	0.00	82.3
1.00	1.00	0.00	99.0
2.00	0.20	0.00	18.2
4.00	0.20	0.00	17.5
6.00	0.20	0.00	18.0
8.00	0.20	0.00	17.1
1.00	0.10	0.10	10.8
1.00	0.10	0.20	12.6
1.00	0.10	0.40	15.3
1.00	0.10	0.60	18.0
1.00	0.10	0.80	21.6
1.00	0.10	1.00	24.3
1.00	0.40	0.00	40.5 ^a

^acontained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of ethanol by MCC at 298 K

Solvents	$10^5 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)	Solvents	$10^5 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	27.5	Acetic acid	4.46
1,2-Dichloroethane	33.9	Cyclohexane	0.89
Dichloromethane	29.5	Toluene	9.12
DMSO	99.0	Acetophenone	44.7
Acetone	28.2	THF	14.7
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	51.3	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	10.5
Butanone	22.4	1,4-Dioxane	16.6
Nitrobenzene	34.7	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	7.94
Benzene	10.9	Carbon disulfide	4.27
Ethyl acetate	11.7		

The activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of the nine aliphatic alcohols are linearly related ($r = 0.9852$). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated^{11,12}

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters for oxidation of alcohols, RCH₂OH, by MCC

Alcohol (R)	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹) at				ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	0.72	2.34	7.74	22.5	81.3 ± 0.7	-40 ± 2	93.1 ± 0.5
Me	44.1	99.0	225	468	56.3 ± 0.5	-92 ± 2	83.5 ± 0.4
Et	72.0	162	360	702	53.8 ± 0.2	-96 ± 1	82.3 ± 0.2
<i>n</i> -Pr	126	261	540	999	49.3 ± 0.3	-107 ± 1	81.0 ± 0.2
<i>n</i> -Bu	144	282	594	1080	48.9 ± 0.1	-107 ± 1	80.7 ± 0.1
<i>i</i> -Pr	207	405	828	1440	45.4 ± 0.4	-116 ± 1	79.8 ± 0.3
ClCH ₂	0.81	2.25	6.03	14.4	68.8 ± 0.6	-79 ± 2	92.2 ± 0.5
MeOCH ₂	7.02	16.2	41.4	90.0	61.1 ± 0.1	-89 ± 1	87.5 ± 0.1
<i>t</i> -Bu	1930	2970	4630	6600	29.7 ± 1.0	-150 ± 3	74.4 ± 0.8
MeCD ₂ OH	7.42	17.3	40.5	88.2	60.5 ± 0.5	-95 ± 2	88.7 ± 0.4
k_H/k_D	5.94	5.72	5.56	5.31			

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, oxidation of [1,1-²H₂]ethanol was studied. The results showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2).

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of ethanol was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvent was limited due to the solubility of MCC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was

from this plot is 455 ± 30 K. The correlation was tested and found genuine by applying Exner's criterion¹³. An Exner's plot between log k_2 at 288 K and at 318 K was linear ($r = 0.9966$). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from the Exner's plot is 494 ± 37 K. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the alcohols are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in rate are governed by the changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of activation.

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent and the other acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of MCC to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile (2).

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar QFC¹⁴.

Solvent effect : The rate constants of the oxidation, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) did not yield any significant correlation in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (LESR) of Kamlet and Taft¹⁵ (3).

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (3)$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.10 + 1.66 (\pm 0.21) \pi^* + 0.9 (\pm 0.17) \beta + 0.19 (\pm 0.16) \alpha \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8536; sd = 0.19; n = 18; \psi = 0.42$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹⁶.

Kamlet's¹⁵ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 85% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion¹⁶ the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* 4).

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's¹⁷ eq. (5) of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (5)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (6), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 0.57 (\pm 0.03) A + 1.79 (\pm 0.02) B - 3.88 \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9973; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.05$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.32 (\pm 0.59) A - 2.89 \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0164; sd = 0.48; n = 19; \psi = 1.01$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.75 (\pm 0.10) B - 3.94 \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9442; sd = 0.11; n = 19; \psi = 0.24$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.39 \pm 0.16 (A + B) - 3.92 \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8204; sd = 0.20; n = 19; \psi = 0.44$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹⁶.

The rates of oxidation of ethanol in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (*cf.* eq. 6) with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 99% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 82% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 82% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.4941$; $sd = 0.34$; $\psi = 0.73$).

Correlation analysis of reactivity : The rates of oxidation of the alcohols failed to yield any significant correlation separately with Taft's¹⁸ σ^* and E_s values eqs. (10) and (12).

$$\log k_2 = -2.17 (\pm 0.33) \Sigma \sigma^* - 1.81 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8571; sd = 0.43; \psi = 0.40; n = 9$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.13 (\pm 0.36) \Sigma E_s - 2.36 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.5822; sd = 0.73; \psi = 0.69; n = 9$$

The rates were, therefore, correlated in terms of Pavelich-Taft's¹⁸ dual substituent-parameter (DSP) eq. (12).

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log k_0 \quad (12)$$

The values of substituent constants were obtained from the compilation by Wiberg¹⁹. The correlations are excellent; the reaction constants being negative (Table 4). There is no significant collinearity ($r^2 = 0.2322$) between σ^* and E_s value of the nine substituents.

Table 4. Temperature dependence of the reaction constant

Temp. (K)	ρ^*	δ	r^2	sd	ψ
288	-1.80 ± 0.01	-0.72 ± 0.01	0.9999	0.008	0.01
298	-1.71 ± 0.02	-0.63 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.007	0.02
308	-1.62 ± 0.03	-0.53 ± 0.01	0.9999	0.003	0.01
318	-1.53 ± 0.02	-0.45 ± 0.02	0.9989	0.005	0.02

The negative polar reaction constant indicates an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. The negative steric reaction constant shows a steric acceleration of the reaction. This may be explained on the basis of high ground state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product aldehyde as well as in the transition state leading to it, the transition state energies of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore, results.

Mechanism :

The observed acid-dependence of the reaction rate may be explained on the basis of a protonation of MCC in a pre-equilibrium (2), with both the protonated and deprotonated forms being active oxidizing species.

The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of an α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The large negative value of the polar reaction constant together with substantial deuterium isotope effect indicate that the transition state approaches a carbocation in character. Hence the transfer of hydride-ion from alcohol to the oxidant is suggested. The hydride-transfer mechanism is also supported by the major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents (Scheme 1).

The hydride ion transfer may take place either by a cyclic process via an ester intermediate or by an acyclic one-step bimolecular process. This postulation is supported by an analysis of the temperature dependence of kinetic isotope effect. Kwart and Nickle²⁰ have shown that a study of the dependence of the kinetic isotope effect on temperature can be gainfully employed to desolve this problem. The data for protio- and deuterio-ethanols, fitted to the familiar expression : $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D \exp(E_a/RT)$ ^{21,22} show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrical transition state which the activation energy difference (ΔE_a) for k_H/k_D is equal to the zero-point energy difference for the respective C-H and C-D bonds (≈ 4.5 kJ/mol) and the frequency factors and the entropies of activation of the respective reactions are nearly equal. The similar phenomena have also been observed earlier. Bordwell²³ has documented a very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step biomolecular processes by hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present study, the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic biomolecular process. It is well established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterized by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer²⁴. Littler²⁵

Acid-independent Path

Scheme 1

has also shown that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI} , involves six electrons and, being a Huckel-type system, is an allowed process. Thus the overall mechanism is proposed to involve formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step, followed by a disproportionation of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Scheme 1). The observed hydrogen-ion dependence can be explained by assuming a rapid reversible protonation of the chromate ester (A) with the protonated ester decomposing at a rate faster than (A) (Scheme 2).

by the usual method²⁷.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, ethanol (2.30 g, 0.05 mol) and MCC (2.22 g, 0.01 mol) were made up to 50 cm^3 in DMSO and kept in dark for *ca.* 15 h to ensure the completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 cm^3) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm^{-3} HCl and kept overnight in refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol and weighed again. The yield of DNP before and after recrystallization was

Acid-dependent Path

Scheme 2

Experimental

Materials : MCC was prepared by the reported method⁶ and its purity was checked by an iodometric method. The procedures used for the purification of alcohols have been described earlier. $[1,1\text{-}^2\text{H}_2]\text{Ethanol}$ (MeCD_2OH) was prepared by Kalpan's method²⁶. Its isotopic purity, as ascertained by its NMR spectra, was $96 \pm 3\%$. Due to the non-aqueous nature of the medium, *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in a polar medium like DMSO it is likely to be completely ionised. Solvents were purified

2.02 g (91%) and 1.79 g (79%), respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of acetaldehyde. Similar experiments with other alcohols led to the formation of DNP of the corresponding carbonyl compounds in yields ranging from 72 to 84%, after recrystallization. Iodometric determinations of the oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures indicated that the oxidation state of the reduced chromium species was 3.90 ± 0.15 .

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large

excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the alcohol over MCC. The temperature was kept constant to ± 0.1 K. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of MCC spectrophotometrically at 370 nm for 80% of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{MCC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was evaluated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{alcohol}]$. Simple and multivariate linear regression analyses were carried out by the least-squares method on a personal computer.

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